

The Role of the Dominant Party of the Republic of Kazakhstan and China's Ruling Party in a Country's Modernization: Similarities and Differences

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Abstract—The purpose of this work is to identify the positive and negative aspects of parties' participation in the country's modernization, which in turn, will help a country to determine the necessary steps to improve the social-economic development. The article considers a question of the role of the dominating party of Kazakhstan and ruling party of China in the country's modernization. Using a comparative analysis reveals differences between the People's Democratic Party "Nur Otan" and the Communist Party of China. It is discussed the policy of carrying out of modernization, the main actions of political parties of both countries with a view of modernization implementation.

Keywords—China's modernization, dominant party, ruling party, modernization of Kazakhstan.

I. INTRODUCTION

ACCORDING to the classical concept, modernization – is the transformation of the traditional agrarian society to an industrial society. The first description of the modernization was reflected in the works of the great thinkers of the 19th century, A. Comte, H. Spencer, K. Marx, M. Weber, E. Durkheim and F. Tennis. Present time, the modernization is also the main object of study of many thinkers and scientists.

Today, modernization of the country is one of the most topical and weighty issues in the life of Kazakhstan and China. Modernization covers a wide range of sectors. As all of us know, after the beginning of modernization in the form of reforms, China started its prompt development period, and despite its economic and social backwardness at that time, has been able to achieve unknown successes in a relatively short historical term. China has been able to raise national economy to such level, which some materially wealthier countries had been unable to do. Modernization deduced China to the front ranks in the international community.

Kazakhstan after the finding independence also entered on a new stage of development. The country has had many old problems remained after the USSR and new problems of the

young state. It was necessary to change all of the government, economic and political systems of the country. Therefore, implementation of large-scale reforms was appropriate. Today we see notable results of these actions on a country's modernizing, and without fail many of us will be agree that in Kazakhstan for the last 20 years of modernization, welfare of the people improved. The country itself has also entered the new stage in the international arena.

Modernization's success or failure directly depends on policy of carry out. In this regard, it is necessary to note the directly and especially influential role of the ruling party of China and dominant party of Kazakhstan. However, activities of parties of two countries have the distinctions and features in carrying out modernization. In this article, our purpose is to open these distinctions, find those features, which can be borrowed for improvement of carrying out of modernization.

II. PEOPLE'S DEMOCRATIC PARTY "NUR OTAN"

The main and leading political party of Kazakhstan is People's Democratic Party Nur Otan. Therefore, in the performance of all the major and influential cases concerning the country dominates this party. Of course, the party carries out the affairs of the country, which permitted by the Constitution of the Republic of Kazakhstan, by the Law of Republic of Kazakhstan "On Political Parties", by the other normative legal acts of the Republic of Kazakhstan and the Charter and program of the party.

Party Nur Otan was created on January 19, 1999, by transforming of the public association. According to the Charter of party, the main purpose of Nur Otan is to achieve the construction of an economically strong, democratic, secular, legal and social state with a development of civil society, the modern competitive political system by the methods of administrative and political work, and in accordance with the program of the Party, one of the objectives is to participate in social, economic and political reforms of country [1]. Of course, all of the reforms of public, economic and political system in Kazakhstan were started a bit earlier, almost immediately after gaining independence on the elaborated program of Head of State. This was not a spontaneous and easy decision, by this time was a little preparation, as there was a strong need for a large-scale change in the country. However, this period was characterized

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by a reduction process after the collapse of the USSR, and after this period was alternated the Asian financial crisis of 1997-1998. Despite the fact that there were changes for the better than first time, but this time was not distinguished with particularly rise in the socio-economic sphere of Kazakhstan. It is only since the new millennium the Kazakhstan's economy has begun to grow rapidly and expand. By that time, Kazakhstan is more or less recovered, identified themselves new horizons that helped guide confidently into the future.

In all, there are three fundamental documents of the party – the "Program", "People's Platform" and "Action Strategy of PDP Nur Otan", which play a significant role in the implementation of all the plans and objectives of the party. The key document of the "Nur Otan" party is the People's Platform "For the prosperity of Kazakhstan and well-being of Kazakhstan citizens: how can we improve the lives of every citizen of the country", which reflecting the prospective vision of the country. In the People's Platform clearly defined the tasks to those targeted efforts of the party in the coming years. This People's platform covered the spheres of social and economic development of the country, including education and science, culture, ethnic harmony, the democratization of society, youth policy, the environment, etc. It is constantly working on the implementation all of the clauses and paragraphs of the People's Platform. A key element in the implementation of this platform is the systematic monitoring of the implementation. The analysis is based on the monitoring of exact and numerical data, provided by the central and local authorities. Monitoring provides the ability to track the favorable and the negative sides of the party. According to the party as a whole, positive dynamics of the implementation of the People's Platform, which once again proves the effectiveness of the party is observed [2]. According with the program of Nur Otan, which was proclaimed in 2007, the main goal of the party – is to achieve modernization breakthrough. According to this program, the economy of the country should work on strategic outstripping growth rate and innovative trends of other countries. It should be based on advanced science and technology of the future. To achieve its goal the Party Nur Otan has identified its way, it is - favorable conditions for the realization of human potential, effective government administration, progressive political system, and favorable domestic and external factors [3]. The concrete plan of the Party to improve the economic condition of the country is that the establishment, strengthening and development of the national leaders campaigns who will be the vanguard of the national economy, competitive "players" in the regional and global economy. According to the Nur Otan, this strategy will establish a public-private partnership in the implementation of breakthrough projects. Creation of corporate leaders must take place through the formation of new companies in growth sectors of the economy, attracting foreign businesses to operate in Kazakhstan, support and, where necessary, the restructuring of existing businesses. In the strategy of action of NDP Nur Otan, there are shows concrete actions and times

of their implementation. The Party marks the development of efficient stock market as an equally momentous task for the country. The reason is that every citizen could be become a co-owner of the share capital of key Kazakh companies in strategic sectors of the economy. Currently (since 2012), this plan is carrying out in the framework of the People's IPO. Particularly focuses on the dynamic development of small and medium-sized businesses, which must be one of the priorities of the economic policy of the country and provide the highest level of the contribution of small and medium businesses to the country's GDP. The party also advocates for the increasing the role of the country in the management of national natural resources, further strengthening of market mechanisms of regulation economic relations between the government and private sectors. Party makes efforts to improve the system of governance of industrial-innovative development, strengthening and effective work of state institutions [4].

III. COMMUNIST PARTY OF CHINA

The Communist Party of China - is the foundation of the PRC. The party is around 90-years-old. Everyone knows that the role of this Party in China is extremely high. This is the ruling party. There are many books have been written about Communist Party of China and China's modernization by many researchers and experts from both foreign and Chinese themselves. For example, among them are such authors as Barry Naughton, Susan L. Shirk, Thomas G. Rawski, He Chuangqi, Gao Fan, Peng Ming, Sun Jian, I.Naumov, V.Portyakov, NLMamayeva, L.Delusin, K.Kokarev etc. Every author is differently treating the issue from different points of view and interests. If the main goal of the Chinese authors is to identify any deficiencies of the Communist Party and their elimination to promote the country's modernizing, foreign authors pursue goals to find something for their country, in search of a better development model. Referring to the previously investigated materials and a new data, we also strive to find the features of the Communist Party of China in the course of modernization, which can be useful for our country in the carrying out of modernization.

There is no need to repeat the history of the founding of the Communist Party of China and the history of Chinese modernization. We know that the Chinese Communist Party has gone not an easy way before the founding of the PRC, and after the founding of the PRC, the Party also had to go through a lot of effort in order to maintain and establish itself in a country's power.

Human history shows that the roles and fate of any kind of political force are closely consistent with the trends, regularity and evolution of the times. Whether or not a party can always keep itself dynamic basically depends on the roles it plays in moving forward history and on the extent of the people's recognition of such a role. Only when a party maintains its vanguard nature will it be entitled to represent the people, exercise state power and properly use the power for the people. The reason why the Party could liberate, enrich and

strengthen China, follow the general trend at every critical moment and continue to initiate reforms amid social development lies in that it has always held to the basic principle of building a party committed to serving the interests of the people and exercising state power for the people.

It has always represented China's demand for the development of advanced productivity, the development direction of advanced culture and the fundamental interests of the majority of the people as well as always retained and developed the vanguard nature of a Marxist party. The Party is always armed with developing Marxism in different times and different stages to maintain its eternal vitality in the process of continuously pushing forward China's modernization and has been ahead of the times when leading social progress [5].

As it is known, the turning point of Chinese history, which created political preconditions for the gradual transition to the profound economic changes, was the third Plenum of the Central Committee of Chinese Communist Party of the 11th convocation in December, 1978. The elaborated strategy of economic reform and opening-up policies – this is that realistic and reasonable way of carrying out of modernization, which took place in China. In ideological terms, a new strategy was developed in the form of the concept of "building socialism with the Chinese characteristics". The modernization of China meant the becoming a state with modern industry, agriculture, science, culture, services and high standard of living and adequate defense [6].

Country's modernization strategy and providing favorable conditions of foreign policy selected by country allows China for over the past three decades of reform to achieve mightily impressive undeniable and obvious results. We are witnesses of that what unprecedented achievements China was able to achieve today due to modernization, and it would be superfluous to repeat it. However, the path and methods of modernization is interesting and useful for us, in that it could be serve us as a model.

IV. SIMILARITIES AND DIFFERENCES

Analyzing the policy of modernization of the Chinese Communist Party and the People's Democratic Party Nur Otan of Kazakhstan we can get some general similarities. Parties of both countries are paying special attention to the science and education. Both parties consider the science and education as a main capital of human to his future and to the general welfare of the country. The young people, who has received a quality education and which is in demand by society – it is the engine of development.

Deng Xiaoping at the beginning of Chinese modernization said that «When China, a vast country with a billion people, has developed its education, it will enjoy an enormous superiority in intellectual resources that no other country can match». He also noted that «The Central Committee has called upon us to do our utmost to develop education, beginning with elementary and secondary education. This is a strategic move. If the Central Committee did not set this task for the Party now, major undertakings would be delayed and history would

hold it responsible». He said that the Party committees and governments at all levels should take educational work seriously and do it well. Noted that everyone should be strict with themselves and spend less time on idle talk and more on real work [7].

And now, in Kazakhstan there are a variety of programs realized to support science and education in the country by the Government of the Republic of Kazakhstan and the People's Democratic Party Nur Otan, headed by the President Nursultan Nazarbayev. Training of competitive, skilled persons for most promising industries and promoting of talented scientific staff are the foundation of the national project "Intellectual nation - 2020", where the core is the human capital. According to the President Nursultan Nazarbayev - on the agenda today is the question of our country's transition to the "knowledge economy". If to quote the words of the head of state, becoming educated and healthy, strong nation, we can build a stronger economy, which in turn will provide all of us a prosperous life and a high level of income. Our formula for future success it is an achievement the high standard of living for every citizen of Kazakhstan through the development of human potential. The Party Nur Otan expounding its program Kazakhstan -2017, as one of its main priorities determines the development of quality education at all levels [8].

Important progress in the modernizing is to strengthen the position of the Party itself. According with the Constitution of the Communist Party of China, the Party must constantly strengthen and improve its Party building, implement a strict inner-control, develop the best tradition of party and style of working, tirelessly raise the level of their party leadership and governance. Thus, the CPC determines four basic requirements, which must be followed in building the party: First, adhering to the Party's basic line. The whole Party must achieve unity in thinking and in action with Deng Xiaoping Theory, the important thought of Three Represents and the Party's basic line. Second, persevering in emancipating the mind, seeking truth from facts and keeping pace with the times. Third, persevering in serving the people wholeheartedly. Fourth, upholding democratic centralism. It is the fundamental organizational principle of the Party and is also the mass line applied in the Party's political activities [9].

People's Democratic Party Nur Otan also considers it is necessary to modernize their activities in order to for further improve the ideological and political competitiveness. According to the assertion of the Party, this requires improving inner-organizational activities, update the structure and organizational work of the party, increasing the role of primary party organizations, such as the main instrument to strengthen the party's influence to society, development of inner discussion on the most pressing issues of the Party and society, the expansion of the social base of the party through the consistent defense of the interests all of the social and demographic groups [10].

Another trend, which traced in the work of the CPC and the NDP Nur Otan it is rejuvenation of party membership. New

course of country's development in the context of globalization, a century of innovation transformation requires the progressive staff. If say about CPC, at the turn of the 60th anniversary of the founding of New China, the Communist Party's leading cadres position at all levels insensibly changed by relatively young people. Today, the CPC make some specific demands to young cadres, for example, to equip with the concept of scientific development, to strive for ideological purity, to focus on the rule of law in governance etc. Communist Party leadership is convinced that with the guiding idea of CPC, which is in step with the times, the institutionalization of change old employees by new, young cadres, can afford and extend the viability of the party.

People's Democratic Party Nur Otan also notes the importance of rejuvenation specialists. One of the evidences in this direction is the creation of the party's youth wing "Zhas Otan". The scope of activities of the "Zas Otan" is varied, but the main goal is to participate in the political life of society, the creation of social, economic, political and other conditions for the full development of the youth of the Republic of Kazakhstan, to increase its spiritual, moral, intellectual and physical potential, social and economic status.

In addition to comprehensive measures for modernization of the economy and social sphere, the leadership of the Communist Party of China also carrying out modernization of the political structure. The CPC as well as NDP Nur Otan, is actively involved in the systematic modernization of the political structure of country. According to the fundamental documents, modernization of the political system is one of the priorities of the Nur Otan Party, but despite the fact that there are positive results, but, it must acknowledge that, neither in China nor in Kazakhstan the political modernization has not yet reached the desired level, it has repeatedly criticized by the Western world, and international experts. This issue requires thorough research.

Clear distinction can be seen in the structures of the two parties. The first party – is the Communist party, the second party – is the People's Democratic Party; However, the main difference between the two parties - is the status and duration of existence. The Communist Party of China is the ruling party of mainland China while the Nur Otan party is dominant party among the other Parties of Kazakhstan. In this sense, the CPC could afford to make decisions for the entire country, and the party Nur Otan has no such authority. CPC is the engine of development of China. But Nur Otan currently can only work within the framework of any of the programs that contribute to the country's development. The Chinese Communist Party was formed before the formation of the PRC, has extensive experience in governance and management of the development of the state of the country, and Nur Otan party as a young party, has to establish itself and gain skills for productive activities.

In China, the modernization carried out as an integral part of the development of the country and in Kazakhstan according to the reporting of party members, it seems, that it is carried out within specific programs. However, it is also

necessary to note that of the Nur Otan party has a distinctive feature, it is - the active implementation of youth policy. Youth policy of the Nur Otan party is the starting point of contact of the Kazakh youth with the social activities and political authorities. Youth organizations, which were created under the Nur Otan party, play a vital role in the dissemination and clarification of the party and government decisions about the development of the country, which in turn may be useful in the implementation and ideas and plans. After all, the young people are not just the hope of the country, also are the generator of powerful ideas.

In fact, there are a number of important programs were realized by the Nur Otan party on the acceleration and improvement modernizing the country, which is the basis of all activities in the process of modernization. However, the important is the visual results of completed work. After analyzing the work of NDP Nur Otan in general, we can observe the activities of the youth wing of Zas Otan, which realizes quite relevant and important event for the development and modernize the Kazakh society. For example, a program initiated by the Zas Otan "With diploma to the village" provided to a lot of remote areas of Kazakhstan graduates, which in turn stimulates the development of rural areas.

V. CONCLUSION

The most fundamental difference between the Communist Party of China and the National Democratic Party Nur Otan in the carrying out of modernization of country - is a theoretical foundation. The Chinese Communist Party because of its extensive experience in the governance and implementation of the country's modernization, sufficiently explored every possible theory from the world modernization, learned a lesson and experience, then taking into account the socio-political and cultural identity of China, makes its own, a new theory on modernization, in other words, the basis for the modernization is modernized.

In China Center for Modernization Research, based on generalizations of the classical and contemporary theories of modernization, developed an original theory of the "second modernization" for China, according to this theory modernization is a complex, systematic, non-linear process, which has a "channel" for the modernization "breakthrough" of China [11]. It developed various theoretical concept, which theoretically indicates the opportunity to make modernization "breakthrough" of China in the group of advanced countries of the world by 2050 [12].

In Kazakhstan, in particular the Nur Otan party, there are not enough theoretical, conceptual frameworks of modernization. In general, in our country modernization itself is not yet fully understood and reconsidered. For a successful modernization, primarily requires thorough elaboration, the study of the problem of modernizing the country, in which can be useful experience of the Communist Party and China as a whole.

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